

New *N*-galactosides : Synthesis of *N*-galactosylated thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and thiocarbamates

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Abstract : The title compounds were prepared by the condensation of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate with several amines, 2-aminobenzothiazole/substituted benzothiazoles and alcohols respectively. The structure of these new *N*-galactoside has been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral studies of some typical cases.

Keywords : *N*-Galactosides, galactosyl isothiocyanate, galactosyl thiocarbamides, galactosyl benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides, galactosyl thiocarbamates.

Introduction

Glycosyl amines, glycosyl guanidine derivatives, glycosyl thiocarbamides have several medicinal applications such as antitumour agent¹, antilukemic agent², antibacterial properties³, anti-metastasis compounds⁴ and in many other ways⁵.

Glycosyl isothiocyanates^{6,7} are important synthetic intermediates in carbohydrate chemistry. They have been used to prepare thioureidosugars⁸, isocyanides⁹, isodithiobiurets¹⁰ etc. These glycosyl isothiocyanates are prepared by the reaction of glycosyl halide with silver¹¹ or potassium¹² thiocyanate. Herein we report the synthesis of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (**1**) by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- α -D-galactopyranosyl bromide with lead thiocyanate.

Glycosyl isothiocyanates react with ammonia and primary amines, benzothiazoles and alcohols to form corresponding 1,3 disubstituted thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and thiocarbamates respectively.

These reactions take place generally with good yields. The advantage of this method is its versatility, being compatible with protected group in the sugar isothiocyanate¹³.

The reactions of lactosyl¹⁴ and glucopyranosyl¹⁵ isothiocyanates with amines and substituted benzothiazoles have been studied so far. Also the microbial activities¹⁶ of benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides having tetra-*O*-benzoyl- β -glucosyl substituent have been studied. So it is of keen interest of synthesise *N*-galactosylated thioamides.

In the present communication we report the synthesis of *N*-galactosylated thiocarbamides, benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides and thiocarbamates by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (**1**) with various amines/ammonia, substituted benzothiazoles and alcohols respectively.

The required amines and alcohols were commercially obtained, while the 2-amino benzothiazole/substituted

Scheme 1

where,

R¹ = (a) Phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl, (h) H

R² = (a) H, (b) 4-Cl, (c) 5-Cl, (d) 6-Cl, (e) 4-methyl, (f) 5-methyl, (g) 6-methyl

R³ = (a) Ethyl, (b) *n*-propyl, (c) isopropyl, (d) isoamyl, (e) *n*-butyl

Scheme 2

benzothiazoles were prepared by the earlier known method¹⁷.

D-galactopyranosyl bromide¹⁸ with lead thiocyanate (Scheme 1).

Tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) was prepared by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl-α-

The title products (3a-h, 5a-g, 7a-e), have been prepared by the condensation of tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-

Table 1. 1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl-3-ary/H-thiocarbamides (3a-h)

Reactants : (i) Tetra-*O*-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) (0.005 M, 2 g)

(ii) Aryl amines/ammonia (2a-h) (0.005 M)

Sr. No.	Products (3a-h)	Amines (g)	Yield (%)	m. p. (°C)	[α] _D ²² (CHCl ₃)	Analysis (%) : Found (Required)		R _f (CCl ₄ : EtOAc)
						N	S	
1.	3a	Aniline (0.45)	65.58	128	+133.94° (c, 0.373)	5.66 (5.80)	6.76 (6.63)	0.69 (3 : 2)
2.	3b	<i>o</i> -Cl-Aniline (0.64)	71.69	176	+117.64° (c, 0.340)	5.46 (5.42)	6.12 (6.19)	0.73 (3 : 2.2)
3.	3c	<i>m</i> -Cl-Aniline (0.64)	62.26	124	+91.85° (c, 0.326)	5.37 (5.42)	6.24 (6.19)	0.79 (3 : 2.2)
4.	3d	<i>p</i> -Cl-Aniline (0.64)	69.81	140	+155.19° (c, 0.386)	5.49 (5.42)	6.23 (6.19)	0.86 (3 : 2.1)
5.	3e	<i>o</i> -Toluidine (0.54)	54.90	172	+205.88° (c, 0.340)	5.69 (5.64)	6.49 (6.45)	0.89 (3 : 2.1)
6.	3f	<i>m</i> -Toluidine (0.54)	66.66	160	+242.42° (c, 0.333)	5.58 (5.64)	6.41 (6.45)	0.71 (3 : 2.1)
7.	3g	<i>p</i> -Toluidine (0.54)	68.23	110	+187.50° (c, 0.320)	5.55 (5.64)	6.51 (6.45)	0.77 (3 : 2.3)
8.	3h	Ammonia (0.08)	74.51	126	+105.26° (c, 0.386)	6.81 (6.89)	7.93 (7.78)	0.57 (3 : 2.1)

Table 2. 1-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-3-substituted benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (5a-g)Reactants : (i) Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) (0.005 *M*, 2 g)(ii) 2-Aminobenzothiazole/substituted benzothiazole (4a-g) (0.005 *M*)

Sr. No.	Products (5a-g)	Benzothiazoles (g)	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	[α] _D ²⁹ (CHCl ₃)	Analysis (%) : Found (Required)		R _f (CCl ₄ : EtOAc)
						N	S	
1.	5a	2-Amino... (0.75)	54.15	138-140	+74.46° (c, 0.94)	7.64 (7.79)	11.95 (11.87)	0.57 (3 : 2.1)
2.	5b	... 4-Chloro- (0.92)	68	115-117	+49.67° (c, 1.00)	7.11 (7.32)	11.29 (11.16)	0.60 (3 : 2)
3.	5c	...5-Chloro- (0.92)	51	172-174	-38.71° (c, 1.03)	7.18 (7.32)	11.06 (11.16)	0.66 (3 : 2)
4.	5d	...6-Chloro- (0.92)	61	158-160	-39.73° (c, 1.00)	7.21 (7.32)	11.21 (11.16)	0.62 (3 : 2.2)
5.	5e	...4-Methyl- (0.82)	74	155-157	+91.22° (c, 0.98)	7.41 (7.59)	11.32 (11.57)	0.71 (3 : 2)
6.	5f	...5-Methyl- (0.82)	77	118-120	+69.54° (c, 1.00)	7.49 (7.59)	11.66 (11.57)	0.76 (3 : 2)
7.	5g	...6-Methyl- (0.82)	74	175-177	+49.01° (c, 1.02)	7.44 (7.59)	11.71 (11.57)	0.80 (3 : 2)

galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) with several amines (2a-h), substituted benzothiazoles (4a-g) and alcohols (6a-e).

Results and discussion

Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) :

Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) has been prepared by condensation reaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- α -D-galactopyranosyl bromide (0.01 *M*, 4.1 g) and lead thiocyanate (0.01 *M*, 3.28 g) in boiling sodium dired xylene (40 mL) for 3 h. After completion of reaction the xylene solution is filtered. The excess of solvent has been removed by distillation. The sticky residue obtained was triturated several times with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80 °C), to afford a solid. It was then purified from CHCl₃ and petroleum ether. The purity of compound was checked by TLC. It was found desulphurisable when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution (Scheme 1).

1-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-3-aryl/H thiocarbamides (3a-h) (Scheme 2) (Table 1) :

Condensation of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1), (0.005 *M*, 2 g) and amines/ammonia (2a-h, 0.005 *M*) was carried out in boiling benzene on water bath for 3 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC. After the reaction has been completed, the excess solvent was distilled off and sticky residue obtained was triturated with petroleum ether (60-80 °C) to afford a solid. All

products formed were purified from CHCl₃-petroleum ether. They showed positive charring test when heated with conc. H₂SO₄ and desulphurization was noticed when boiled with alkaline plumbite solution.

1-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-3-substituted benzothiazolyl thiocarbamides (5a-g) (Scheme 2) (Table 2) :

The reaction between tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) (0.055 *M*, 2 g) and 2-aminobenzothiazole/substituted benzothiazoles (4a-g, 0.005 *M*) in benzene (25 mL) has been carried out on boiling water bath for about 4 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and the sticky residue obtained was triturated with petroleum ether to afford a solid. It was crystallized from ethanol-water to give the products (5a-g).

N-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-*O*-alkyl thiocarbamates (Scheme 2) (7a-e) :

N-Tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-*O*-alkyl thiocarbamates (7a-e) were obtained, by condensation reaction between tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1), (0.005 *M*) with various alcohols (6a-e, 20 mL) for 3 h. After completion of reaction, the reaction mixture was poured in ice-cold water with vigorous stirring to obtain the products (7a-e). All products were crystallized from ethanol-water.

The purity of compounds (3a-h), (5a-g) and (7a-e)

Table 3. *N*-Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-*O*-alkyl thiocarbamates (7a-e) Reactants : (i) Tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (1) (0.005 M, 2 g) (ii) Alcohols (6a-e, 20 mL)

Sr. No.	Products (7a-e)	Alcohols	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	[α] _D ³⁵ (CHCl ₃)	Analysis (%) : Found (Required)		R _f (CCl ₄ : EtOAc)
						(N)	(S)	
1.	7a	Ethyl	68.18	136	-136° (c, 0.74)	6.81 (6.89)	7.93 (7.88)	0.62 (3 : 2.1)
2.	7b	<i>n</i> -Propyl	65.21	128	-87.5° (c, 0.8)	3.02 (3.11)	7.02 (7.12)	0.76 (3 : 2)
3.	7c	Iso-propyl	52.17	158	-25.3° (c, 0.79)	2.99 (3.11)	7.00 (7.12)	0.70 (3 : 2)
4.	7d	Isoamyl	61.22	114-115	87° (c, 0.74)	3.00 (2.93)	6.61 (6.70)	0.86 (3 : 2.2)
5.	7e	<i>n</i> -Butyl	46.20	210(d)	52.6° (c, 0.76)	3.11 (3.02)	6.91 (7.01)	0.82 (3 : 2)

Satisfactory C and H analysis was found in all cases.

has been checked by TLC. The physical data is given in Tables 1, 2 and 3 and spectral analysis¹⁹⁻²¹ of typical cases has been discussed in Experimental part.

The high value of coupling constant between H₁-H₂, H₁-NH ranging between 8-12 Hz showed that the products formed have β -configuration²²⁻³⁰.

Experimental

General methods :

Melting points are uncorrected, optical rotations [α]_D were measured on a Equip-Tronics digital polarimeter model no. EQ 800 in CHCl₃. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI (4000-450 cm⁻¹) FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer for a sample in CDCl₃ solution with TMS as an internal reference. The mass spectra were recorded on a Joel SX-102 and Micromass Quattro II triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

(1) Yield 55%, m.p. 92 °C [lit.²⁴ : 92-94 °C]; [α]_D³² = +53.57° (c, 0.373); R_f : 0.71 (CCl₄ : EtOAc, 3 : 2); IR (KBr) : ν 2104 (-N=C=S), 1751 (C=O), 1239 (C-O), 1029 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 5.41 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.33 (1H, t, *J*_{1,2} 9 Hz, H₂), 5.04 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, H₃), 5.00 (1H, d, *J*_{1,2} 9 Hz, H₁), 4.13 (2H, d, *J* 6 Hz, H_{6,6'}), 3.97 (1H, t, *J* 6 Hz, H₅), 2.18-1.99 (12H, 4s, 4COCH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 389 (M⁺), 331, 211, 169, 109 (Found : C, 6.19; H, 4.80; N, 3.44; S, 8.34. Calcd. for C₁₅H₁₉NO₉S : C, 46.27; H, 4.88; N, 3.59; S, 8.22%).

(3a) IR (KBr) : ν 3364 (N-H), 2954 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1373 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1051 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.19 (1H, s, NH), 7.49-7.19 (5H,

m, Ar-H), 6.64-6.61 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH), 5.84 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.43 (1H, d, H₄), 5.2-5.16 (1H, dd, *J* 3 Hz, H₃), 5.10-5.06 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₂), 4.13-4.05 (3H, m, H_{5,6,6'}), 2.17-1.89 (12H, m, 4COCH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 482 (M⁺), 331, 211, 169, 109 (Found : C, 52.33; H, 5.46; N, 5.66; S, 6.76. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₆N₂O₉S : C, 52.28; H, 5.39; N, 5.8; S, 6.63%).

(3b) IR (KBr) : ν 3341 (N-H), 2967 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1371 (C-N), 1228 (C-O), 1052 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.04 (1H, s, NH), 7.55-7.28 (4H, m, Ar-H), 6.78-6.73 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH), 5.76 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.48-5.44 (1H, s, H₄), 5.21-5.16 (1H, dd, H₃), 5.12-5.05 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₂), 4.16-4.06 (3H, m, H_{5,6,6'}), 2.17-1.81 (12H, m, 4COCH₃); Mass (*m/z*) : 517 (M⁺+1), 331, 211, 169, 109 (Found : C, 48.76; H, 4.88; N, 5.46; S, 6.12. Calcd. for C₂₁H₂₅N₂O₉SCl : C, 48.83; H, 4.84; N, 5.42; S, 6.20%).

(3g) IR (KBr) : ν 3342 (N-H), 2966 (Ar-H), 1750 (C=O), 1371 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1051 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 8.05 (1H, s, NH), 7.27-7.25 (2H, d, Ar-H), 7.08-7.06 (2H, d, Ar-H), 6.58 (1H, d, *J* 8.7 Hz, NH), 5.85-5.79 (1H, t, *J* 8.7, 9.3 Hz, H₁), 5.43-5.42 (1H, s, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.20-5.15 (1H, dd, *J* 3 Hz, H₃), 5.05 (1H, t, *J* 9.3 Hz, H₂), 4.13-4.05 (3H, m, H_{5,6,6'}), 2.39 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.16-1.69 (12H, m, COCH₃), Mass (*m/z*) : 496 (M⁺), 331, 211, 169, 109 (Found : C, 53.18; H, 5.61; N, 5.55; S, 6.51. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₈N₂O₉S : C, 53.22; H, 5.64; N, 5.64; S, 6.45%).

- (3h) IR (KBr) : ν 3403 (N-H), 2965 (ali. C-H), 1748 (C=O), 1372 (C-N), 1229 (C-O), 1021 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.36 (2H, s, NH_2), 7.08–7.05 (1H, d, J 9 Hz, NH), 6.61 (1H, bs, H_1), 5.50–5.49 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, H_4), 5.30–5.17 (2H, m, H_2 , H_3), 4.41 (1H, m, H_6), 4.23–4.20 (1H, dd, J 4.5 Hz, H_5), 4.11–4.07 (1H, m, H_6), 2.28–1.84 (12H, m, COCH_3) (Found : C, 44.28; H, 5.49; N, 6.81; S, 7.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_9\text{S}$: C, 44.33; H, 5.41; N, 6.89; S, 7.88%).
- (5a) IR (KBr) : ν 3453 (N-H), 2979 (Ar-H), 1752 (C=O), 1586 (C=N), 1373 (C-N), 1226 (C-O), 1056 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.73–7.29 (5H, m, NH, Ar-H), 6.38 (1H, s, NH), 5.45–5.30 (2H, m, H_1 , H_3), 5.19 (1H, bs, H_4), 5.08 (1H, t, J 9 Hz, H_2), 4.17–3.98 (3H, m, $\text{H}_{5,6,6'}$), 2.19–2.00 (12H, m, 4COCH_3); Mass (m/z) : 540 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 48.84; H, 4.59; N, 7.64; S, 11.95. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{25}\text{N}_3\text{O}_9\text{S}_2$: C, 48.97; H, 4.63; N, 7.79; S, 11.87%).
- (5d) IR (KBr) : ν 3415 (N-H), 2966 (Ar-H), 1752 (C=O), 1610 (C=N), 1370 (C-N), 1226 (C-O), 1056 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.65 (1H, m, NH), 7.43–7.19 (3H, m, Ar-H), 6.16 (1H, bs, NH), 5.50–5.30 (2H, m, H_1 , H_3), 5.18–5.16 (1H, d, J 3 Hz, H_4), 5.00–4.97 (1H, t, J 9 Hz, H_2), 4.16–3.97 (3H, m, $\text{H}_{5,6,6'}$), 2.19–1.98 (12H, m, 4COCH_3); Mass (m/z) : 574 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 46.13; H, 4.23; N, 7.21; S, 11.21. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_3\text{O}_9\text{S}_2\text{Cl}$: C, 46.07; H, 4.18; N, 7.32; S, 11.16%).
- (5g) IR (KBr) : ν 3468 (N-H), 2967 (Ar-H), 1752 (C=O), 1599 (C=N), 1372 (C-N), 1227 (C-O), 1057 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 7.44–7.08 (4H, m, NH, Ar-H), 5.46–5.29 (2H, m, H_1 , H_3), 5.15 (1H, bs, NH), 5.04–4.97 (2H, m, H_4 , H_2), 4.15–3.96 (3H, m, $\text{H}_{5,6,6'}$), 2.36 (3H, m, Ar- CH_3), 2.21–1.97 (12H, m, 4COCH_3); Mass (m/z) : 544 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 49.97; H, 4.26; N, 7.44; S, 11.71. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{27}\text{N}_3\text{O}_9\text{S}_2$: C, 49.90; H, 4.33; N, 7.59; S, 11.57%).
- (7a) IR (KBr) : ν 3368 (N-H), 2926 (ali. C-H), 1751 (C=O), 1372 (C-N), 1222 (C-O), 1079 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 6.87–6.84 (1H, d, NH), 5.57 (1H, s, H_1), 5.45 (1H, bs, H_3), 5.17 (2H, bs, H_4 , H_2), 4.56–4.41 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_2$), 4.14–3.97 (3H, m, $\text{H}_{5,6,6'}$), 2.22–1.62 (12H, m, 4COCH_3), 1.37–1.25 (3H, m, CH_3); Mass (m/z) : 436 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 44.28; H, 5.49; N, 6.81; S, 7.93. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_{10}\text{S}$: C, 44.33; H, 5.41; N, 6.89; S, 7.88%).
- (7c) IR (KBr) : ν 3362 (N-H), 2984 (ali. C-H), 1750 (C=O), 1371 (C-N), 1225 (C-O), 1075 (C=S); ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) : δ 6.77–6.74 (1H, d, NH), 5.63–5.41 (3H, m, H_1 , H_4 , CH), 5.21–5.12 (2H, m, H_3 , H_2), 4.15–4.03 (3H, m, $\text{H}_{5,6,6'}$), 2.20–1.93 (12H, m, 4COCH_3), 1.63–1.24 (6H, m, $(\text{CH}_3)_2$); Mass (m/z) : 450 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$), 331, 169, 109 (Found : C, 48.17; H, 6.09; N, 2.99; S, 7.00. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{27}\text{NO}_{10}\text{S}$: C, 48.10; H, 6.01; N, 3.11; S, 7.12%).

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